

Report on Digital Research Infrastructures

This contribution contends that the research community, internationally, and across many domains of inquiry from the life and physical sciences to the social sciences and humanities, must engage more effectively with the evolution and provision of infrastructures for managing research data. In particular, we identify that the liability for data preservation in all but a few activities, together with responsibility for realizing the potential of new technologies for methodological advances, has rested with practitioners. Critically, over the last two decades the volume of research data generated, and ultimately lost—primarily through technology obsolescence and lack of strategic and financial planning—has increased dramatically¹. Yet institutional libraries have not been provided with the significant incremental resources necessary, nor made responsible for, building expertise and infrastructure in this complex field; neither have new organizations been established expressly for the purpose. Instead, funding agencies have focused on derestricting access to literature arising from publicly-funded research activities; and upon on-going confrontations with the publishing industry that have arisen from this. In the mean time, commercial enterprises have been encouraged to extend proprietary storage solutions for use in the research community, which creates not only new vulnerabilities from supplier lock-in, but also restricts accessibility for future researchers, since these solutions were designed for commercial purposes.

Pre-COVID Circumstances

For the vast majority of practitioners, success with navigating the risks of building and operating reliable workflows and realizing the potential of digital methods remains a matter of chance. Even for those eschewing digital methods, and requiring only library stacks, pens and paper—contemporary modes of communication and the establishment and maintaining of scholarly and institutional reputations now depend on digital tools such as citation management and persistent identifier strategies. One outcome of this situation is that research data generated by publicly-funded research activities is regularly and irretrievably lost, both unintentionally and, in the absence of effective preservation solutions, through being simply discarded. Conspicuously, even data resources proposed as the principal outputs of research projects with digital components are seldom accessible for more than five years before succumbing to technology obsolescence and budgetary constraints. In a period of increasing climate-related disruption, re-emergence of social and political tensions and, in some domains, monotonically diminishing research budgets, unimpeachable research outputs have never been more important. Yet, while large-scale Artificial Intelligence applications (AIs) are already consuming literature and media resources on a vast scale to build knowledge products behind corporate defenses, researchers outside still struggle to future-proof digital research outputs which are essential for independent verification of their results.

Notable exceptions to these circumstances are communities such as biodiversity, genomics and high-energy physics, which have organized large-scale data resources that are shared by researchers globally. Analysis products generated from these resources by researchers nevertheless become increasingly vulnerable as they move from centrally-maintained and funded infrastructures to local institutional or project-based IT. Expiration of research grants and ensuing loss of personnel and expertise constantly endangers research data even in these communities.

Systemic institutional failures are at the root of these difficulties, though fluid responsibility boundaries make them challenging to examine without appeal to discourse analysis. Contemporary preoccupation with Data Management Planning (DMP), the European Digital

¹ vines, cornwell

Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) present comprehensive illusions that the challenges of research data management are being effectively addressed, while diverting financial support away from addressing core problems and, in some cases, contributing to them. Such are the scales of these schemes that attempting to analyze them succinctly here is fruitless. What it is possible, however, is to describe current circumstances in which researchers, and principal investigators (PIs) in particular, can themselves precipitate change and improve the long-term accessibility of research data. Accessibility, which is prominent in the FAIR Principles acronym², belies preservation. Find-ability, Interoperability, and Reuse are meaningless without effective packaging and preservation of data for future access. And the preservation of large volumes of information in digital form still presents significant challenges because, ultimately, it is specific physical media which are inscribed with digital information. PIs adoption decisions in relation to the emerging tension between open source research data repository software platforms³ on one hand, and commercial data storage services presented as preservation solutions, on the other, presents an opportunity to address research data challenges decisively. Central to this discussion is the growing and deleterious role in national infrastructures of cloud-based storage products provided by large technology enterprises: so-called 'hyperscaler' solutions. For the research community to make informed decisions in what might in the future be regarded as a crucial period for digital methods in many disciplines, clear visibility of the practical goals and challenges of data preservation is essential.

Post-COVID Landscape

The caesura created by the COVID-19 pandemic precipitated significant alteration of research data infrastructure trajectories. On one hand scholars, especially cultural heritage specialists and historians with research projects in mid-execution, were suddenly denied access to physical collections and archives, and the shortcomings of equivalent data services became disturbingly apparent. On the other hand research instruments based on large language models which had been in development throughout the previous decades started to become available to the global scientific community as practical and low-cost alternatives to manual workflows. This greatly increased both the scale of digitized printed sources which could be considered, even in modest research activities, and also the sophistication of scientific questions that could be addressed. By June 2023, when the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention reported that the COVID excess-deaths metric had fallen below 1% and pronounced the pandemic officially over, AI had become a major media focus globally.

This fundamental change in the public's relationship with information technology also subtly affects the goals of research data preservation. Firstly the value of digitizing archive sources is now evident. The necessity for successive generations of scholars to retread the labors of predecessors—long regarded as a badge of apprenticeship—is increasingly problematic. A cohort of PhD students has just been required to modify their research programs because of closure of conventional archives for extended periods. It is evident that previous archive users have seldom digitized, far less made available for long-term remote access by the research community, the sources that they painstakingly discovered and employed. This effectively eliminates independent verification of conclusions or building upon existing research activities: only unsubstantiated final publications may remain. For their part, few archives operate systematic digitization programs and

² The 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship' were established in 2016 to provide guidelines to improve the Find-ability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

³ For example, Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) <https://en.unesco.org/freeandopensourcesoftware>

libraries are retreating from provision of comprehensive digital services because of financial forecasts of long-term hosting. In a parallel development, escalating political tensions have in the same years led to withdrawal of access for foreign scholars to many archives in China and the Russian Federation. Digitization already carried out by visiting scholars from the rest of the world may, for the foreseeable future, become the sole representation of such material available to the international research community, and if it is lost through data stewardship failures then considerable uncertainty and cost is associated with regaining access to those resources. Increased probability of future pandemics and escalating chaos linked to the climate emergency compound these challenges.

Secondly, digitized archival records, literature and cultural objects are already consumed with little restriction by machine applications. Outcry by authors at the time of writing that their works are *being* harvested by commercial AIs only illustrates limited comprehension of the underlying strategies and abilities of large IT enterprises. The landmark *Smith v. Maryland* case of 1979 (<https://www.oyez.org/cases/1978/78-5374>), which judgement applied only to numbers dialed using a public telephone exchange, has formed the core of legislation which is now applied to a broad spectrum of information that is voluntarily given to third parties. The Maryland Court of Special Appeals deemed that Smith had no expectation of privacy to cover the telephone numbers he had dialed. Maryland was cleared of any violation of Smith's Fourth Amendment rights over its use of numbers he dialed without obtaining a warrant while investigating him. Undebated inflation of the scope of information at the core of *Smith v. Maryland* in the intervening years now emboldens governments to attempt electronic surveillance of citizens internationally, using any technologies at their disposal. This led Edward Snowden, an employee of U.S. National Security Agency contractor Booz Allen Hamilton, in June 2013, to protest by leaking a significant volume of classified information to the press. In conjunction with 'fair use' legislation and employee non-disclosure agreements, the same case law has enabled IT enterprises and publishers to develop large language model (LLM) -based AI applications by systematically harvesting data deposited by clients on their infrastructures, as well as internet data. Notably, this includes the libraries and museums and scientific literature which Google and IBM and Microsoft and other corporations prominently 'contribute' to digitizing. Acquisition of GitHub by Microsoft was unchallenged by any legislative agency. The recommendation of current national research infrastructures (e.g. The European Commission's ARCHIVER project for EOSC) to employ commercial hyper-scalar storage solutions is further evidence of the tacit expectation that commercial AIs will gain access to any media and research available digitally which is not already in the process of being lost or which is protected by robust defenses.

These new circumstances represent a significant shift in the focus of the digital research methodologies of the first decades of this century. Previously, researchers developed and operated digital research instruments and workflows for the analysis of information generated experimentally or discovered in historic literature. This information was often entered manually as datapoints in pursuit of singular final outcomes, and provenance relating to the source and the location within it of the datapoint, while usually noted, was itself not defined in a structured way suitable for machine access. Crucially, persistent identifier architectures were not employed to link datapoints with their original context in the sources in which they were discovered. Indeed, the majority of historic sources cannot yet be discovered electronically. For example, a manuscript held in a special collection of the Weston Library⁴ was accessible only by its shelf mark until 2023, even though it is mentioned in the Catalogue of English Literary Manuscripts. Consequently, outputs produced by research activities based on historical sources have not, heretofore, been

⁴ Medieval and early modern manuscripts from the collection of Richard Rawlinson (1690-1755) <https://digital.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/collections/rawlinson/>.

linked in a persistent way to the sources themselves, and must refer to the holding institution to enable reproducibility of results or extension of the research. Standards such as the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF), the Web Annotation Data Model (WADM) and persistent digital object identifier architectures (DONA) developed before COVID-19 made possible the digital preservation of connections between historical sources and research outputs. However, although IIIF has become widely supported since its establishment as an international consortium in 2015, the effective preservation of information discovered in physical source materials for future use by both human researchers and machines has only become practical with support of both IIIF and WADM by research data repositories since 2022. The Rawlinson BtA 2 manuscript, above, which is the subject of a new research project is now accessible via PID⁵.

Whereas databases, simulations and other outputs of digital methods, in the humanities and social sciences in particular, have previously been conceived as distinct from historic sources to which they refer, making these outputs preservable, and therefore fully accessible to the wider research community requires that source materials themselves must similarly be accessible. In the post-COVID landscape, where ubiquitous AI-based instruments are now at the disposal of researchers, and can be tasked with a wide range of activities, a likely trajectory arises in which AIs may become involved in defining research questions and determining susceptible source materials and methodologies autonomously. This does not imply the more distant advent of Artificial *General* Intelligence (AGI) technology, but the capabilities and access of existing commercial AIs to research data already makes clear the new overlap between the research community and IT enterprises. In turn, a process of reorientation of traditional research has commenced, which was presaged by the Open Science (OS) movement⁶, towards a privileging of source materials and the creation of open data resources guaranteed to remain accessible in the long term. Digital research methodologies based on the primacy of outputs will similarly be realigned to focus on the identification of historic sources, and their delivery for use by the broader community, as well as the pursuit of specific research questions. Outputs relating to research questions will be envisaged as linked to source data, rather than vice-versa. However, it is not clear whether even AGIs will gain the agency to identify and themselves make machine-accessible arbitrary source materials in the physical world, and a long-term relationship between researchers and AIs in this area seems likely. Emerging research data repository technologies are therefore crucial—not only for the creation and preservation of data resources integrating historic sources and human research outputs, but also as means for unrestricted human access to AI research outputs, rather than these fruits becoming sealed in corporate infrastructures.

A Brief History of Research Data Repositories

Ensuring that research data outputs can be reused with multiple software platforms, and yet-to-be-developed technologies in the future, is a key task of research data management. Where this requires conversion of the way data is represented, for example by exporting in a technology-agnostic format from a proprietary software application, then a clear transition in status from active research to preservation is established. Attention to making data traceable is also essential: guaranteeing fixity is to no avail without certainty about identity. This requires that description of the contents of data files, together with their relationship to the research activity in which they were generated, is captured as metadata. In turn, metadata files have to be linked to their referents so that they cannot be separated from them, regardless of data management decisions in later

⁵ [20.500.14202/hasdai.uyx37-j5ywq](https://doi.org/10.500.14202/hasdai.uyx37-j5ywq)

⁶ <https://www.orion-openscience.eu/resources/open-science>

stewardship. If metadata is not available to future users, even carefully-preserved data files require potentially prohibitive forensic analysis before any attempt at utilisation. As time elapses it becomes increasingly difficult to identify potential software applications that might have been used to create digital outputs, or determine their significance to the original research, and their potential value evaporates.

The process of creation and management of metadata to permit effective future discovery and reuse of research data files is a key function of a class of digital infrastructure components called research data repositories. While data is being generated, transferred and processed it is often referred to as ‘in motion’. As soon as research activities deem that data has become static—even if succeeded by later versions—its status ‘at rest’ should trigger commitment to a data repository for secure long-term management.

The emergence of pervasive configuration management repositories such as Git⁵ in the software development community and, in particular increasing use of its GitHub commercial instance across a wide range of scientific domains, has influenced researcher behaviour in respect of managing software program data at rest. Significantly, neither GitHub or Google’s Workspace encourage research practitioners to persist data managed using their products in to independent long-term data preservation infrastructures. Such configuration management repositories promote metadata relating principally to contributions towards *software development projects*, and the management of dependencies between them. However, they provide scarce support for provenance metadata relating to external objects and processes that are not software programs. In contrast, metadata standards for research data repositories have emerged through the activities of libraries and government agencies internationally since at least 1965⁶. More recent metadata schemes such as that supported by DataCite⁷ are implemented by research data repositories presented in what follows here, but detailed discussion of both metadata and persistent identifier (PID) technologies is not addressed in this article.

Repository Software Platforms

Data repositories form a class of digital infrastructure components which support the management of data at rest—providing web-based interfaces for administrators and users, as well as APIs for machine access and external organisations including libraries. Originally developed to disseminate and preserve research *outcomes*—predominately scientific literature in digital form, and more recently also key datasets—the data repositories currently in use include proprietary services (which are not addressed here), as well as repositories based on multiple open source software platforms supported by international consortia. These consortia comprise commercial enterprises, research organisations and universities. Repository ‘instances’, based on the shared software platform, are tailored to the individual requirements of the member organisations running them. Repository instances can form ‘generalist’ repositories—for example supporting multiple faculties at a university, or ‘corpus’ repositories, addressing more specific requirements of individual research activities and special collections. Because they can be configured more closely for content with a common focus, corpus repositories are able to provide more support for those data types than generalist repositories. For example, by implementing domain-specific metadata and search models it is possible to offer discovery based on the contents of records, as well as generic terms such as author and date of creation. Significantly, corpus repositories are also able to allocate more resources individually to fewer records. Underlying IT constraints limit maximum data capacity and the performance available for searching repository records in response to concurrent

user queries. In contrast, generalist repositories must potentially support millions of heterogeneous records, and therefore limit the size of data files associated with each record, as well as implementing a data model common to all of them. This means that interim and analysis research data, as well as final outcome publications and specific datasets can be preserved routinely using corpus repositories. Nevertheless, consortium member organisations are able to employ the shared repository software platform for both corpus and generalist repository requirements. Members collaborate on maintenance necessary to address changing development environment and operating system dependencies, upon compliance with standards and the network security landscape, and on developing new functionality. All organisations benefit from shared planning and testing of this engineering work. The alternative—of each organisation developing and maintaining different repository software—is untenable.

Consortia have created multiple repository platforms, which have been in service in parallel within their memberships for several decades, but in the last five years more smaller organisations are adopting these software platforms. For example DSPACE repository technology has its origins in work at MIT and Hewlett Packard Labs before 2002. In 2009 DSPACE joined with the Fedora Commons organisation to form not-for-profit DuraSpace. Fedora repository technology was originally developed by Cornell University's Digital Library Research Group in 1997, which together with The University of Virginia established the Fedora Repository project—later, Fedora Commons. In 2019 DuraSpace merged with LYRISIS, an umbrella group of more than 1000 Libraries in 28 countries, first established in 1936. The Samvera Community also uses the Fedora software platform, but it utilises Blacklight and Solr discovery technologies and the Library of Congress's Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) standard. In contrast, origins of the Invenio repository platform can be traced to the SPIRES project of CERN and the National Accelerator Laboratory at Stanford University (SLAC) in the 1960s. SPIRES, which continues to operate as iNSPIRE-HEP⁹ is a database of particle physics literature, and was one of the first research data resources to be accessible via the World Wide Web. The CERN Document Server infrastructure, based on this experience, was launched in 2000 and moved to the recently-developed Invenio Digital Library platform in 2006.

It is notable that these activities—arising in both the physical sciences and the social sciences and humanities—have converged into two open source software platforms—Fedora under the LYRISIS umbrella and Invenio through the InvenioRDM¹⁰ Consortium. Although these consortia include the largest organisations in their memberships, collaboration is essential for the development and operation of repositories, because of their complexity and large scale, as well as the long-term financial commitment which they demand. Founding-member organisations generally provide financial support in-kind through assignment of their own software development and administrative personnel, or through financial support of external costs such as contract engineers. In some cases funding agencies have joined consortium governing bodies as observers—sometimes contributing financially at modest levels. Early participation of large institutions has been a factor in other organisations' decisions to join consortia and adopt these software platforms. For example California Institute of Technology (Caltech) has operated an Invenio-based repository since 2015¹¹ and Austrian and German universities and Northwestern University Feinberg School of Medicine have contributed significantly to the more recent InvenioRDM Consortium (discussed further below). Smaller, recently-joining organisations, while not providing engineers or funding, nevertheless support valuable testing and internationalisation activities. Although protracted, this mode of developing and maintaining complex software responds to shared recognition by these organisations of the need to retain capacity to manage, make accessible and preserve research data. Relying in their early stages on individuals to precipitate these initiatives while at the same time performing other job functions—and continuing releases of significant new functionality decades later, indicating that development will continue in coming years—repository consortia are

not ideal in their approach. However, this self-organising process demonstrates widespread rejection within the research community of the inadequate functionality and un-forecastable long-term costs of operating proprietary alternatives, and a consortium model is now repeated in the development of other key components of research data infrastructure.

Repository Interoperability Requirements

Repositories are constructed using mature software development environments, and they were not expected to remain in service for more than a few decades before being replaced with repository platforms developed using newer software technologies. Notwithstanding this, investment in developing records using both the Invenio and Fedora software platforms has not been fully reusable when later updated versions of those platforms were released. Significant additional work was necessary to reimplement all of the records in existing repositories when they moved to the new version of the platform, even though attention had been paid to making the data comprising the individual records technology-agnostic. This was because the search and metadata models, as well as logic for access control and underlying database technologies employed by new versions of the repository software platforms were not compatible with existing implementations.

To address these losses, further development has been required to allow repository records to be used across different existing and future repository software platforms without repeating the investment of creating them. Both repository records' metadata and attached files, and potentially multiple versions of these resources (where they evolve during research processes or through subsequent enrichment) need to be made portable. Requirements for repository interoperability technologies were the subject of an RDA Working Group established in May 2016¹². A subsequent workshop organised by the Bodleian Digital Library in September 2017¹³, which was attended by multiple Fedora repository consortia, proposed creating The Oxford Common File Layout (OCFL) standard—which is based on Unix concepts dating from the late 1960s standardised by the POSIX¹⁴ community. Since 2017 an international consortium, led by Cornell, Emory, Harvard, Oxford and Stanford Universities, has been established to manage, develop and support OCFL, creating important additional opportunities for preservation of research data. OCFL can potentially be used to gather repository records into single, self-contained digital archive objects. The process of making repository records self-describing—also referred to as dereferencing—eliminates the requirement for external information such as schemata, otherwise connected via external links. Such references would otherwise prevent archive objects being employed effectively if the objects they link to no longer exist at a future date. Gathering the complete records of a dereferenced corpus repository using OCFL permits future-proof digital objects to be generated which do not require specific technologies nor infrastructure to make full use of them. Notably, both the Fedora and InvenioRDM consortia have already implemented preliminary OCFL support¹⁵. In combination with OCFL, repository platforms can now be used to both manage research data services for global communities via the contemporary internet, and also to archive research corpora for portability between repository software platforms and, critically, for compatibility with future technical platforms.

Very Long-term Preservation

Dereferenced repository records, packaged as archive objects using OCFL are suitable for offline storage using media designed for long-term access, compared with rotating disk technologies, which have guaranteed operating lifetimes of just a few years. An industry consortium, formed in 2004, comprising Hewlett Packard Enterprise Company, International Business Machines Corporation and Quantum Corporation¹⁶ collaborates to support Linear Tape Open (LTO) technology. LTO manages the manufacture and on-going development of cartridge-based

magnetic tape storage, which has become an IT industry standard—shipping approximately 9.1 million cartridges in 2021. LTO has both an historical track record and a forward roadmap of approximately twenty years each, and its current generation provides 18TB uncompressed cartridge capacity (a terabyte is one thousand gigabytes, or one thousandth of a petabyte), with 30 year life¹⁷ at approximately €200 per unit in small quantities. This enables corpora to be replicated and stored at multiple locations¹⁸ cost-effectively. Critically LTO creates an ‘air-gap’—protecting repository archives from online security hazards—as well as bestowing resilience by simplifying automated management of copies of corpora, in geographical locations having orthogonal disaster threats, through robotic tape libraries.

¹ For example, Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) <https://en.unesco.org/freeandopensourcesoftware>

² The ‘FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship’ were established in 2016 to provide guidelines to improve the Find-ability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

³ Secure Data Recovery, Inc. report March 8th 2023, concludes that the operating life of rotating magnetic disk products from six major vendors fell below 36 months for the first time in 2022. Annualised failure rates (AFRs) for Solid State Disks (SSDs) have also risen to 2% across multiple vendors during the same period.

⁴ The National Digital Stewardship Alliance’s 2019 guideline, recommends maintaining at least two copies in separate locations, while noting three copies in geographic locations with different disaster threats is stronger. NDSA Levels of Preservation Revisions Working Group, “Levels of Digital Preservation, 2019 LOP Matrix, V2.0 (OSF, October 14, 2019), <https://osf.io/2mkwx/>.

⁵ Git is a distributed version control system (software configuration management—SCM) originally used for coordinating work among programmers. It was developed by Junio Hamano and Linus Torvalds and first released in 2005. [https:// git-scm.org](https://git-scm.org). GitHub is a commercial instance of Git, with more than 100M users. Its parent company is Microsoft Corporation which purchased GitHub in 2018. <https://github.com/>

⁶ Computer scientist Henriette Avram developed the machine-readable cataloging standard (MARC) from 1965.

⁷ DataCite was founded by organisations from 6 countries in 2009, and 5 additional organisations were approved by the International Council for Science in 2010. <https://www.datasite.com/>

⁸ Fedora (Flexible Extensible Digital Object Repository Architecture) is a digital asset management repository architecture for building institutional repositories, digital archives, and digital library systems. <https://fedora.lyrasis.org> This is distinct from The Fedora Project, which is sponsored by RedHat, Inc., a software company founded in 1993 and now a subsidiary of IBM. <https://docs.fedoraproject.org/>

⁹ INSPIRE defines itself as a “community hub” which helps researchers share and find accurate scholarly information in high energy physics. <https://inspirehep.net/>

¹⁰ InvenioRDM is a turn-key research data management repository software platform. <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>

¹¹ <https://librarytechnology.org/pr/20852/caltech-selects-tind-library-management-system>

¹² RDA Research Data Repository Interoperability WG <https://www.rd-alliance.org/node/50279/case-statement>

¹³ <https://blogs.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/digital/2017/07/06/fedora-and-hydrasamvera-camp-at-oxford-sept-4-8-2017/> and <https://ocfl.io/1.1/spec/>

¹⁴ Originating in 1988 and now maintained as IEEE Std 1003.1-2017 by a joint group including ISO and IEC

¹⁵ CERN and Data Futures GmbH demonstrated export for InvenioRDM corpus repositories during 2021, and developed software library support for the Python community. <https://pypi.org/project/ocflcore/>

¹⁶ Seagate Technology was early original LTO consortium partner, but its magnetic tape technology was bought by Quantum Corporation in 2004.

¹⁷ Recovery of data reliably from LTO depends on storage temperature and humidity, as well as usage. Cartridges accessed frequently by robotic libraries will have lower lifetimes than those shelved in controlled environments.

However, the automated replication of LTO contents on to contemporary generation cartridges on a periodic basis, which is effectively lossless when multiple copies are maintained at different locations, means that large repository archive objects can be stored with high reliability and low cost for long periods.

¹⁸ The National Digital Stewardship Alliance's 2019 guideline, recommends maintaining at least two copies in separate locations, while noting three copies in geographic locations with different disaster threats is stronger. NDSA Levels of Preservation Revisions Working Group, "Levels of Digital Preservation, 2019 LOP Matrix, V2.0 (OSF, October 14, 2019), <https://osf.io/2mkwx/>.

Peter Cornwell is a research fellow at the Institute for East Asian Studies at ENS-Lyon, a visiting fellow at the Institute for European Global Studies in Basel and professor at the Institute for Modern and Contemporary Culture at Westminster University, London. He is also European co-chair of the Research Data Alliance Preservation Tools, Technologies and Policies Group, community lead for OCFL and WADM in the InvenioRDM Consortium and an expert advisory board member of BiCIKL EU Research and Innovation action in Biodiversity 101007492.